

MATURITY AND PROVENANCE OF THE ALBIAN BIMA SANDSTONE IN WURO-DOLE AND ENVIRONS, YOLA ARM, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Bima Sandstone at Wuro-Dole and environs was studied for its level of maturity and source area (provenance). In evaluating its textural maturity and provenance, field mapping was carried out and representative samples were subjected to physico-chemical and mineralogical analyses. The sandstone consists of some primary sedimentary structures: cross-beddings and ripple marks. Strike measurements of these primary structures plotted on current rose diagrams indicated SSE-NNW and NE-SW/NW-SE directions. The Bima Sandstone is averagely made up of medium grained, poorly-sorted, fine skewed and very leptokurtic, angular sandy sediments. Petrographic study revealed about 57.3% quartz, 18.8% feldspar, 3.5% mica, 10.5% rock fragment, 5.1% cement, 2.4% heavy minerals, and 2.5% matrix. On the basis of framework composition of quartz, feldspar and mica + rock fragment, the sandstones of Wuro-Dole were grouped as lithic subarkose with a few of lithic arkose variety. They are generally immature. Concentrations of major oxides include SiO₂ (75.9%), Al₂O₃ (14.2%), Fe₂O₃ (4.6%), CaO (0.6%), MgO (0.16%), Na₂O (1.2%), MnO (0.12%), TiO₂ (0.14%), and K₂O (2.6%). These geochemical results further validate that of mineralogical analysis in that the sandstone consists mainly of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Na₂O and K₂O which is reflection of the presence of quartz and feldspar. Heavy mineral separation showed that the Bima Sandstone is made up of rutile, zircon, tourmaline, sphene, staurolite, sillimanite, and apatite; these heavy mineral assemblages are indicative of mainly felsic igneous and high grade metamorphic rocks. Granite and gneiss suites of both Southeastern and North Central Basement Complexes of Nigeria have been suggested as the probable source areas of the Bima Sandstone.

KEYWORDS: Maturity, Provenance, Bima Sandstone, Yola Arm, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Sedimentary rocks possess three basic properties- mineral composition, texture, and structures that are traceable to their source area(s) and environment(s) of deposition. The main objective of provenance study is to deduce the characteristics of the source area(s) from measurements of compositional and textural properties of sediments supplemented by information from other lines of evidence such as directional sedimentary structures. Textural maturity is an important key to the physical nature of the environment of deposition (Palaeogeography), since it provides a descriptive scale that indicates the effectiveness of the environment in winnowing, sorting and abrading the detritus furnished to it (Folk, 1968).

The Bima Sandstone has been widely studied by many workers such as Falconer (1911), Raeburn and Brynmor (1934), Barber *et al* (1954), Jones (1962), Carter *et al* (1963), Reyment (1965), Offodile (1989), Ojo (1999), Braide (1992a and 1992b). Most of these works are based on the Chad Basin, Upper Benue Trough, and Middle Benue Trough where the Bima Sandstone outcrops, but not much has been done on its provenance. The intent of this sedimentary provenance and maturity study is to reconstruct and interpret the history of the sediments from the initial erosion of the parent rocks to the final burial of the detritus of the Albian Bima Sandstone in Wuro-Dole and Environs using both field evidences and laboratory analyses-

particularly the heavy minerals separation method. The study area is located in the vicinity of latitudes 9° 17' 45" to 9° 23' 00"N and Longitudes 12° 35' 30" to 12° 41' 00"E (Fig. 1). This covers a surface area of about 102 square kilometres.

REGIONAL GEOLOGY OF THE YOLA ARM

The Yola Arm is the east-west extension of the Upper Benue Trough that connects the Nigerian basins to other rifts in Africa to form a network of West Africa rift systems (Benkhelli, 1989). Sedimentation generally started in the Upper Benue Trough during the 4 Albian when a great thickness of continental sands and clays-the Bima Sandstone- was deposited unconformable on the Precambrian crystalline basement rocks (Carter *et al* 1963; Offodile, 1989; Ojo, 1999). This was followed by a marine transgression that occurred during the Cenomanian leading to the deposition of transitional beds of sandstones and alternating mudstones and shelly limestones of the Yolde Formation. These passed upwards into a predominantly marine sequence of Turonian-Senonian age. This marine sequence is made up of Jessu Formation, Sekule Formation and Numanha Shale in the Yola Arm; while their lateral equivalents of Gongila and Pindiga Formations were deposited in the Gongola Basin. Continental conditions resumed in the Maastrichtian and resulted in the deposition of the Lamja Sandstone in the Yola Basin while Gombe Sandstone was deposited in the Gongola Basin (Table 1).

The Bima Sandstone was named by Falconer (1911) as the oldest formation occurring at the base of the sedimentary successions in the Upper Benue Trough. Guiraud (1990) described it as the basal unit reflecting the syn-tectonic deposition of sediments as the basin evolved. It is generally extensive and forms ridges and sometimes flat-lying. It stretches to other bounding basins- the Middle Benue Trough to the south-west and the Chad Basin to the north east. Its thickness ranges from 100-3,000m (Offodile, 1989). It is subdivided into 3 parts namely: the Lower Bima Sandstone (B1), the Middle Bima Sandstone (B2) and the Upper Bima Sandstone (B3) (Carter *et al* 1963; Offodile, 1989). The Lower Bima Sandstone (B1) is made up of about 400m thick of sandstones and argillaceous rocks. It is the basal unit of the Bima Sandstone sequence and is not exposed in any part of the entire Upper Benue Trough. The Middle Bima Sandstone (B2) comprises about 800m thick of coarse-grained sandstone with clays and shales, while the Upper Bima Sandstone (B3) is generally the thickest, consisting of about 1,700m of coarse sandstones. Carter *et al* (1963) assigned Upper Albian to Lower Turonian age to the Bima Sandstone. The Upper Bima Sandstone that outcrops in the study area is the main subject of this present study. It is overlain by the Yolde Formation.

The Yolde Formation is made up of a variable sequence of sandstones and shales that marks the transition from continental to marine sedimentation. The sandstone occurrence is suggestive of a beach environment (Opeloye and Obaje, 2005). It is dated as Lower Turonian (Carter *et al* 1963). The Dukul Formation overlies the Yolde Formation and it is composed of a sequence of shales and thin limestones. The limestone is highly fossiliferous- containing mainly ammonites (vascoceratids) that have been used to date it as lower Turonian (Carter *et al* 1963; Ehinola *et al* 2005). The Jessu Formation consists of alternating sequence of grey, white and brown shales and light brown, sandy mudstones with subordinate sandstones. An Upper Turonian age is assigned to it from its fossil evidence (Carter *et al* 1963). A sequence of shales and limestones succeeds the Jessu Formation, and this sequence is termed as Sekule Formation. It is similar to the Dukul Formation and it is also fossiliferous. An Upper Turonian to Santonian age has been assigned to it. The Numanha Formation marks the end of the marine conditions and it is made up of black shales with occasional bands of sandstone, nodular mudstone and limestone. The stratigraphic succession of the Yola Arm terminates with the deposit of clastic Lamja Sandstone. It consists of parallel laminated sandstone with interbeds of thin limestone, coal seams and fossiliferous shale. A Campanian age is assigned to it. The central axis of the rifted basin is lined with Tertiary magmatism such as the Biliri phonolites, Longuda basalts, and Ngurore columnar joints that extruded the Cretaceous sediments (Carter *et al* 1963).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A dual phase data acquisition methodology was adopted- field mapping exercise and laboratory techniques.

Field practice/study: This is a practice in geologic research work targeted at describing the rock types and structural features. Both systematic and random sampling methods were used in this study. The field study involved a detailed field mapping on a scale 1:10,000 and the observed rock types were described in terms of colour, grain size, grain shape, mineralogical composition, etc. A Global Positioning system (G.P.S.) was used for accurate sample location. Orientations of structural features such as beddings (cross-beddings and ripple marks) were systematically measured and mapped. Good exposures were logged (6 lithologic profiles) and drawn to scale (Fig. 2a and b). Well-labeled representative rock samples were obtained for laboratory analyses. Readings of azimuths of planar structures were fed into stereostat software (www.rockware.com) that generated rose diagrams.

Laboratory Techniques: The representative samples obtained were subjected to granulometric, thin section (Petrographic), heavy minerals separation and geochemical analyses. Extraction of provenance related information from sediment grain size distributions as discussed by Weltje and Prins (2003) was adopted in this study.

Granulometric Analysis: Fifteen (15) sandstone samples were air dried and carefully disaggregated in a mortar by a rubber-padded pestle to obtain about 100grams of the disaggregated sample. The 100grams of each disaggregated sample was weighed out using the Harvard Trip digital balance and sieved by means of a set of U.S. standard sieves using the Ro-tap electro-mechanical sieve shaker (M-Tyler) for 15 minutes. Samples retained in each sieve were weighed and their corresponding frequencies and cumulative frequencies obtained. Cumulative frequency curves were plotted. Statistical parameters (graphic mean, standard deviation, inclusive graphic skewness, and kurtosis) were computed (Table 2) using formulae proposed by Folk and Ward (1957).

Thin section (Petrographic) Analysis: Twenty (20) samples were selected for thinsection analysis. The thin-section preparation was based on methods described by Ireland (1971). Both friable and consolidated samples were used; the friable samples were initially impregnated prior to cutting, in order to harden the samples. The samples were each mounted with polished side on a glass slide using Canada balsam. The mounted sample was ground initially with a coarse abrasive and later with sludge of fine abrasive on a glass until the slide was fine or thin enough for individual mineral identification. The prepared thin sections were examined under a flat stage Petrographic microscope for minerals identification and their modal composition determined by point-counting. Mineral identification was based on its optical properties outlined in basic optical mineralogical texts.

Heavy Minerals Separation Analysis: This involved the selective analysis of specific minerals- the heavy minerals that are resistant to the physico-chemical alteration resulting from weathering, transportation, deposition and diagenesis. Each air-dried sample was passed through a forty-mesh (U.S standard sieve, 420 microns or 0.42mm) brass screens onto clean weighing paper. The fraction of each sample smaller than 420 microns (medium sand and smaller on the Wentworth scale) was then washed in distilled water to remove the fine fractions. About 15g of each sample were separated using standard bromoform heavy liquid techniques. The heavy mineral grains were washed, dried, and mounted on glass slides using Canada balsam. Mineral grains in the heavies were identified by standard petrographic techniques (Tickel, 1965) using a polarizing light microscope (M-Meiji). The percentage of the heavy minerals in each sample was determined by counting 150 to 250 grains per samples using a gridded microscope slide.

Geochemical Analysis: Selected representative samples were subjected to a geochemical analysis of sediment whole-rock composition using Atomic Absorption Spectrometric (AAS) method. This involved sample crushing (pulverizing), powdering and disintegration using acids (concentrated Hydrogen Fluoride and Boric acids). This was followed by measurement of major elemental composition using AAS machine.

INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

Textual Properties of the Bima Sandstone

Results and interpretations of the grain size analysis are presented in Table 2. The calculated graphic mean size of the sandstones varies from 0.16 Φ to 2.21 Φ (coarse- to fine-grained) with an average mean size of 1.24 Φ (medium grained). Standard deviation is a measure of sorting. The standard deviation ranges from 0.98 Φ to 1.77 Φ (moderately to poorly- sorted) with an average of 1.39 Φ , poorly sorted sandstones. Inclusive graphic skewness of the sandstones varies from -0.16 to 0.58 (coarse skewed to strongly fine skewed) with an average of 0.07 indicating fine skewed. Kurtosis ranges from 0.6 to 3.4 with an average of 1.61; these imply that they are very platykurtic to extremely leptokurtic and on the average very leptokurtic respectively. Results of the grain size analysis (Table 2) show that these sandstones are about 53% medium grained and 33% coarse grained, suggesting deposition under a high-energy environment. About 93% of the sediments are poorly sorted, an indication of fluctuating depositional currents (Tucker, 1988). This poorly- sorting may also be as a result variable current velocity and sediments deposition close to their source area.

Mineralogical Composition of the Bima Sandstone

The results of petrographic study carried out on 20 sandstone samples of the Bima Sandstone are presented in Table 3. This study revealed that the sandstones are averagely made up of about 57.3% quartz, 18.8% feldspar, 3.5% mica, 10.5% rock fragments, 2.4% heavy minerals, 5.1% cement, and 2.5% matrix. The relatively high SiO₂ (average 75.9%), Al₂O₃ (average 14.2%), K₂O (2.6%), and Na₂O (1.2%) indicated by the geochemical analysis (Table 4) confirms the presence of quartz and feldspar as the main mineral component, while the occurrence of Fe₂O₃ (average 4.6%) is suggestive of the ferrogized nature of some of the sandstones. The cementing material is mainly siliceous (quartz) and occasionally iron oxide mineral. The grains are mainly sub-angular to angular, medium to coarse grained, and moderately to poorly- sorted. On the basis of classification of sandstones using framework composition of quartz (Q), feldspar (F), and rock fragment + mica (L) on a ternary diagram (Fig 3a); the Bima Sandstone is grouped as lithic sub-arkose with a few samples indicating lithic arkose (McBride, 1963).

DISCUSSION

Maturity of the Bima Sandstone

Weltje and Von Eynatten (2004) reported that chemical alteration and mechanical break down of source rocks followed by sorting of particles during transport and deposition, lead to preferential enrichment of specific materials in certain grain-size fractions and hence sediments composition tends to be a function of grain size. Therefore, suitable analytical approaches to sediment provenance also depend on grain size. The grain sizes of the Bima sandstone range from medium to coarse (Table 2) is indicative of deposition under a relatively high energy of flow and a probable short distance of transportation as evidenced from a relatively abundance of feldspar – a less stable mineral – in the Bima Sandstone. The angular to sub-angular shape of the Bima Sandstone is an indication of a short distance of transportation or closeness to the source area. The mineralogical and textural properties are the diagnostic parameters used in the determination of sediment maturity (Pettijohn, 1984). The appreciable concentration of feldspar (Table 3), the dominance of sub-angular to angular shape (Fig. 4), and the poorly sorted nature of the sandstones of the study area, all suggest that they are both texturally and mineralogically immature. The ternary diagram (Fig. 3a) clearly depicts that over 80% of the sandstone facies in the study area are lithic sub-arkose while others are sub-arkose and lithic arkose. A formula adopted by Hubbert (1962) as a measure of maturity index (i.e. Z.T.R. Index) was applied to these sandstones, giving an average mode of 54% (Table 5); corresponding to immature sediments.

Provenance: Measurement of palaeocurrent is a vital part of the study of sedimentary provenance, current/wind direction(s) and palaeogeography. Sedimentary structures prominent in the Bima Sandstone in Wuro Dole and environs include imbricate structures and beddings (cross-beddings, planar cross-beddings, trough cross-beddings, ripple marks, etc) (Fig. 2a and b). The planar cross-bedding was used in the determination of palaeocurrent direction for the Bima Sandstone and it corresponds to the direction of maximum angle of dip, while the asymmetry of the ripples gives the palaeocurrent direction. Strike measurements imputed into the package stereostat generated current rose diagrams (Fig. 5) showing that the ancient current directions were mainly SSE-NNW for the cross-bedding and NE-SW/NW-SE for the

ripple marks respectively. These current rose diagrams showed a strong preferred orientation, with most of the azimuths falling in quadrants with clearly defined modes. The rose diagrams indicate a unimodal to bimodal pattern, that is, the sediments were probably supplied from one or two source areas respectively. The palaeocurrent pattern exhibited by the sandstones of Wuro-Dole and environs shows that the sediments were sourced mainly from the south eastern part and partly from the southwestern part of the study area.

Microscopic examination of the heavy minerals contained in the sandstones of the study area revealed both opaque and non-opaque minerals (Table 5) and (Fig. 4C and D). The opaque mineral is made up of about 19.6% while the non-opaque minerals consist of about 20.6% zircon, 11.6% rutile, 13.0% tourmaline, 10.4% apatite, 8.6% sillimanite, 4.9% staurolite and 11.4% sphene. According to Friedman and Sanders (1978), and Pettijohn (1984), these heavy mineral assemblages in any sandstone suggest a probable igneous and metamorphic parent rocks. They have shown that the occurrences of zircon, tourmaline, apatite, and sphene suggest a felsic igneous source while rutile is indicative of mafic igneous origin. The kyanite, sillimanite, and staurolite are evidence of high grade metamorphic source. The sandstones consist of both monocrystalline and polycrystalline quartz aggregates, but the monocrystalline is dominant; this is suggestive of a probable granitic origin. The results of the geochemical analysis (Table 4) revealed that the Bima Sandstones consist of relatively high SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Na₂O, K₂O, and CaO; these suggest a quartz and feldspar-rich source area.

A comparative overview of the framework composition of the sandstone with the work of Dickinson *et al* (1983) on QFL ternary diagrams (Fig. 3b) showed that some of the sandstones are of a recycled origin (provenance). Considering the regional geology of the study area, the Older Granites and the Migmatite-gneiss complex of the South Eastern Basement (Umeji, 1988) as well as those of the North central Basement Complexes (Oyawoye, 1972) are probable source areas of the Bima Sandstone at Wuro Dole and environs.

CONCLUSIONS

Bima Sandstone outcropping at Wuro-Dole and environs was mapped and studied for its textural characteristics and mineralogical compositions in order to establish maturity and provenance for it. The geological mapping exercise revealed that the study area is made up of medium grained, poorly-sorted, cross-bedded and ripple-marked sandstones. The sandstones, which are generally immature, have colour range from white to reddish-brown; the reddish brown is evidenced from the relatively high iron oxide content in some sandstones.

Mineralogically, it is composed of mainly quartz, feldspar, mica, rock fragments and heavy mineral assemblages – rutile, zircon, tourmaline, sphene, apatite, sillimanite, and staurolite. The sandstones have been classified as lithic sub-arkose and a few lithic arkose. They are characterized by a relatively high concentration of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, K₂O, and Fe₂O₃, while other oxides (MgO, MnO, and TiO₂) are relatively low. Palaeocurrent plots based on the strike measurements of the associated cross-beddings and ripple marks showed NNW – SSE and NE – SW/NW – SE directions respectively. A combination of the texture, geochemical analysis, mineralogical composition, palaeocurrent pattern and the heavy mineral assemblages; was used to suggest the Older Granite and Gneiss suites of Southeastern and North –Central Basement Complexes as the provenance for the Bima Sandstone at Wuro Dole and environs.

REFERENCES

- BARBER, W., TAIT, E.A. and THOMPSON, J.H. 1954: The Geology of the Lower Gongola. Ann. Rept. Geol. Surv. Nigeria. Pp. 5 – 20.
- BENKHELIL, J. 1989: The origin and evolution of the Cretaceous Benue Trough, Nigeria. Jour. African Earth Sciences. Vol. 8. pp. 251-282.
- BRAIDE, S. P. 1992a: Studies on the Sedimentation and Tectonics of the Yola arm of the Benue Trough: Facies Architecture and their Tectonic significance. Jour. Mining and Geology. Vol. 28, No. 1, pp. 23 – 31.

- BRAIDE, S. P. 1992b: Morphology and Depositional history of An Aptian – Albian Crevasse splay in the Bima Sandstone, Yola Basin Benue Basin. Bull. Nig. Assoc. Petroleum Expl, Vol. 7, No. 1 pp 46-50.
- CARTER, J.D., BARBER, W., TAIT, E.A. and JONES, J.P. 1963: The Geology of parts of Adamawa, Bauchi and Bornu Provinces in North-eastern Nigeria. Geol. Surv. Nig. Bull. 30.109p
- DICKINSON, W.R. Beard, L.S; Brakenridge, G.R. Erjavee, J.L; Ferguson, F.C. Imman, K.F; Knepp, R.A; Lindberg, F.A; and Ryberg P.T. 1983: Provenance of North American Phanerozoic sandstones in relation to tectonic setting. Geol. Soc. Amer. Bull. 94. pp.
- EHINOLA, O.A., Joshua, E. O. Opeloye, S.A. and Ademola, J.A., 2005: Radiogenic Heat Production of the Cretaceous sediments of Yola Arm of Nigeria Benue Trough: Implications for Thermal History and Hydrocarbon Generation. Jour. Applied Sciences, Vol. 5, No. 4, pp. 696 – 701.
- FALCONER, J.D. 1911: The Geology and Geography of Northern Nigeria, London.
- FOLK, R.L 1968: Petrology of Sedimentary Rocks, Hemphills, Austin Texas, 172p.
- FOLK, R. L. and WARD, W. 1957: Brazos River Bar. A study of significance of Grain-size Parameters. Jour. Sed. Pet. Vol. 27, pp. 3 – 26.
- FRIEDMAN, G.M. and Sanders, J.E. 1978. Principles of Sedimentology. John Willey and Sons. New York. 792p.
- GUIRAUD, M. 1990: Tectono – Sedimentary framework of Early Cretaceous continental Bima Formation, Upper Benue Trough, N.E. Nigeria. Jour. African Earth Science. Vol. 10. pp. 341 – 353.
- HUBERT, J. F. 1962: A Zircon – Tourmaline – Rutile Maturity Index and Interdependence of the composition of Heavy Mineral Assemblages with the cross composition and Texture of Sandstones. Jour. Sed. Pet. Vo. 32 No. 3 pp. 440 – 450.
- IRELAND, H. A., 1971: Preparation of Thin-sections. In: Carvier, R.E. (Ed.): Procedures in Sedimentary Petrology. John Willey & Sons, New York. Pp. 369-383.
- JONES, G.P. 1962: Deformed Cross-Stratification in Cretaceous Bima Sandstone, Nigeria. Jour. Sed. Pet. Vol. 32. pp. 231-239.
- McBRIDE, E.F., 1963: Classification of common Sandstones. Jour of Sedimentary Petrology . Soc Econ. Pal. Min. Tulsa Oklahoma. Vol. 33. pp. 664-669.
- OFFODILE, M.E., 1989: A Review of the Geology of the Cretaceous of the Benue Valley. In: KOGBE, C.A. (Ed.) Geology of Nigeria. Rock View Nigeria Ltd. Jos. Pp. 365- 376.
- OJO, O.J. 1999: Depositional Environments, Palynological and organic Geochemical studies of Gongola and Yola Basins, Nigeria: Implications for Hydrocarbon Potential. Unpubl. Ph.D. These, University of Ilorin, Ilorin.
- OPELOYE, S.A. and Obaje, N.G. 2005: Ostracods from the Yola Arm, Upper Benue Trough, Nigeria. Global Jour. Geol. Sc. Vol. 3, No. 2. pp. 179 – 185.
- OYAWOYE, M.O. 1972: The Basement Complex of Nigeria. In: Dessauvage, T.F.J. and Whiteman A.J. (Eds.), African Geology. University of Ibadan, Nigeria. Pp. 67-99.
- PETTIJOHN, F.J., 1984: Sedimentary Rocks. 3rd Ed., CBS Pub. & Distr., Delhi. 628p.
- RAEBURN, C. and Brynmor, J., 1934: The Chad Basin; Geology and Water Supply. Bull. Geol. Surv. Nigeria. No. 15.
- REYMENT, R. A. 1965: Aspects of Geology of Nigeria. Univ. Ibadan Press, Ibadan. 145p.
- TICKEL, F.G. 1965: The Techniques of Sedimentary Mineralogy. Elsevier Publishing Company, New York. 220p.
- TUCKER, M.E., 1988: Sedimentary Petrology: An Introduction. ELBS ed. Blackwell Scientific Publ. 252p.
- UMEJI, A. C. 1988: The Precambrian of south eastern Nigeria, a Magmatic and Tectonic Study. In: Oluyide, P.O., Mbonu, W.C., Ogezi, A.E., Egbuniwe I.G., Ajibade A.C. and Umeji, A.C (Eds.); Precambrian Geology of Nigeria. A publication of the Geological Survey of Nigeria. Pp. 69-75.
- WELTJE, G.J. and Prins, M.A., 2003: Muddled or Mixed? Inferring Palaeoclimate from size distributions of deep-sea clastics. Sed. Geol. Vol. 162, pp. 39-62.
- WELTJE, G.J., and Von Eynatten, H., 2004: Quantitative Provenance Analysis of Sediment: Review and Outlook. Sed. Geol. Vol. 171, pp. 1-11.

Fig. 2A: Lithologic section of the Bima Sandstone showing its characteristic beddings observed at location 16 OVE of study area.

Fig. 4: Photomicrographs of some selected sandstones in Wuro Dole and Environs: A and B: medium grained sandstone with mainly Feldspar (FD) and Quartz (QZ) grains (under cross nicols, x 80) C and D: Heavy Mineral grains (under cross nicols, x 80), composed principally of zircon (ZC), rutile (RT), tourmaline (TM), apatite (AP), silimanite (SM), staurolite, sphene, and the opaques (OP)

Fig. 5. Composite Current Rose Diagrams for (A) Cross-bedded and (B) rippled sandstones of Bama at Wuro-Dole and environs.

Table 1: Stratigraphy of the Upper Benue Trough (Modified after Ojo, 1999)

Age	Upper Benue Trough	Lithology	Environment(s) of Deposition
Maastrichtian	Gongola Basin		
Companian	Yola Basin		
Santonian	Gongola Sandstone	Sandstone? Shales? Mudstone?	Continental
Coniacian	Pinjiga Formation	Shales + few bands of mudstone, Sandstone + Limestone	Marine
Turonian	Gongola Formation	Sandstone, Sandy Mudstone + Shales + Limestone	
Cenomanian	Fold Formation	Limestone-Shales series	Transition
Albian	Bima Sandstone	Sandstone + Shaly Limestones	Continental?
Pre-cambrian	Crystalline Basement Rocks	Mainly Sandstones and few clays + shales	
		Granites, Gneisses, Migmatites	Continental

Table 4: Geochemical Composition of representative sandstone samples of the Bima Sandstone of Wuro-Dole and environs

Oxide	Sample Numbers															
	L35 (%)	L7 (%)	L19 (%)	L50 (%)	L48 (%)	L13b (%)	L5 (%)	L13 (%)	L48 (%)	L21 (%)	L46 (%)	L49 (%)	L10 (%)	L5 (%)	L28 (%)	AV. (%)
SiO ₂	75.2	74.8	77.0	75.8	76.7	78.2	75.0	78.0	72.2	76.2	77.0	74.6	76.6	74.6	77.2	75.9
Al ₂ O ₃	15.1	14.9	13.8	15.2	14.5	12.7	14.8	13.0	13.5	14.6	13.6	14.8	14.4	14.6	14.0	14.2
Na ₂ O	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.1	0.9	1.0	1.4	1.2	1.2	1.0	1.4	1.4	1.2	1.2	1.4	1.2
K ₂ O	2.4	2.8	2.6	2.9	2.5	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.6	2.8	2.6	2.8	2.4	2.8	2.6	2.6
CaO	0.1	0.7	0.1	0.9	0.1	0.4	1.0	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.1	0.8	1.0	0.8	1.0	0.6
MgO	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.16
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.4	5.2	4.5	3.9	4.8	5.1	5.0	4.6	4.4	4.4	4.5	5.2	4.0	5.2	4.4	4.6
TiO ₂	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.14
MnO	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.12
Total	100	99.9	99.9	100.1	99.9	99.9	100.1	99.9	99.8	100.0	99.8	99.9	100.1	99.8	100.0	99.9

Table 5: Modal Composition of Heavy Minerals in some representative Sandstones of Wuro-Dole and environs

Sample Number	Zircon (%)	Rutile (%)	Tourmaline (%)	Apatite (%)	Sillimanite (%)	Staurolite (%)	Sphene (%)	Opaque (%)	ZTR Index (%)
L35	37	5	9	19	3	5	2	2	52
L8	34	2	13	15	8	8	17	3	51
L13	13	15	20	-	12	15	20	5	51
L30	18	29	12	-	13	3	23	2	60
L26	15	2	26	34	-	3	12	8	47
L46	30	7	10	17	6	6	4	20	59
L32	32	5	15	18	8	9	-	13	60
L21	18	12	14	-	16	6	9	25	59
L48	12	28	15	5	14	-	6	20	69
L5	18	16	18	-	12	8	18	10	58
L42	36	8	16	5	10	5	-	20	75
L50	28	15	7	6	-	-	16	28	69
L4	-	5	-	15	-	2	10	68	16
L28	5	-	10	22	17	2	4	40	25
L10	10	25	10	-	11	2	12	30	64
Average	20.6	11.6	13.0	8.6	8.6	4.9	11.4	19.6	54

Table 2: Result of the Statistical Parameters obtained from the Grain Size Analysis of some selected Sandstones in Wuro-Dole and Environs

Sample Number	Graphic Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Interpretation
L4	2.21	1.59	0.03	3.40	Fine grained, poorly-sorted nearly symmetrical, extremely Leptokurtic sandstone
L8	1.57	1.13	-0.10	1.94	Medium grained, poorly sorted, nearly symmetrical, very leptokurtic sandstone
L13a	0.61	1.45	0.44	1.83	Coarse grained, poorly sorted, strongly fine skewed, very leptokurtic sandstone
L18b	0.25	1.61	0.12	1.23	Coarse grained, poorly-sorted, near symmetrical, very Leptokurtic sandstone
L24	1.94	1.68	0.32	1.75	Medium grained, poorly-sorted, nearly symmetrical, very Leptokurtic sandstone
L26	1.30	1.45	0.00	1.82	Medium grained, poorly-sorted, nearly symmetrical, very Leptokurtic sandstone
L28c	0.16	1.16	-0.05	1.41	Coarse grained, poorly sorted, fine skewed, very leptokurtic sandstone
L30	0.82	1.13	0.08	1.14	Coarse grained, poorly-sorted, nearly symmetrical, Leptokurtic sandstone
L31	1.57	1.20	0.58	1.71	Medium grained, poorly sorted, strongly fine skewed, very leptokurtic sandstone
L35	1.52	1.25	-0.16	1.50	Medium grained, moderately sorted, coarse skewed, very leptokurtic sandstone
L44	1.08	0.98	-0.11	1.46	Medium grained, moderately sorted, coarse skewed, very leptokurtic sandstone
L46b	1.38	1.77	0.35	1.84	Medium grained, poorly sorted, strongly fine skewed, very leptokurtic sandstone
L47	0.79	1.50	0.38	1.42	Coarse grained, poorly sorted, strongly fine skewed, very leptokurtic sandstone
L50	1.34	1.27	-0.16	1.15	Medium grained, poorly sorted, coarse skewed, leptokurtic sandstone
L51	2.00	1.62	-0.16	0.60	Fine grained, poorly-sorted, coarse skewed, very platykurtic sandstone
Average	1.24	1.39	0.07	1.61	Medium grained, poorly-sorted, nearly symmetrical, very Leptokurtic sandstone

Table 3: Mineralogical Composition of some selected sandstones of Wuro –Dole and Environs

Sample Number	Quartz (%)	Feldspar (%)	Mica (%)	Heavy Minerals (%)	Rock Fragment (%)	Cement (%)	Matrix (%)
L13a	60	15	2	5	10	5	3
L40	60	17	1	-	16	5	1
L31	50	17	4	2	13	10	4
L50	45	22	4	-	15	10	4
L18b	60	17	1	6	10	5	1
L21	55	17	7	5	3	10	3
L8	60	19	4	5	5	5	2
L28c	60	19	4	2	7	5	1
L30	60	22	4	3	10	2	2
L38	60	15	4	2	12	5	2
L13	60	16	2	4	12	3	3
L16	45	24	6	2	16	5	2
L24	52	20	4	-	16	6	2
L33	62	16	2	3	12	3	2
L45	60	24	4	1	6	4	1
L49	60	22	-	2	12	2	2
L5	62	18	3	1	10	2	4
L52	60	16	4	1	10	3	6
L16	54	18	8	2	5	10	3
L38	60	22	2	2	9	2	2
Average	57.3	18.8	3.5	2.4	10.5	5.1	2.5

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